

ions may even be possible by passing the zone chromatographically through the magnetic-field only, if the strength of the magnetic-field is considerably high ($\gg 15$ kilogauss).

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References

- H. KUNKEL and A. TISELIUS, *J. Gen. Physiol.*, 1951, **35**, 89;
A. K. MAJUMDER and H. G. MUKHERJEE, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1956, **15**, 547;
T. WIELAND and E. FISCHER, *Naturwiss.*, 1948, **35**, 29;
R. P. SHUKLA and L. M. LALL, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1969, **46**, 283.
- H. G. MUKHERJEE and D. MAJUMDER, *Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1975, **277**, 205.
- P. W. SELWOOD, *Magneto-Chemistry*, 2nd Ed. 1956, 159.
F. A. COTTON and G. WILKINSON, *Advanced Inorganic Chemistry*, 1969, 1058.

Potentiometric Study of $\text{UO}_2(\text{VI})$ Salicylaldehyde System

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URANYL chelates with phenolic compounds and carboxylic acids have been studied extensively^{1,6}.

In the present study the interactions of uranyl ion with salicylaldehyde in 75% (v/v) dioxane-water mixture at 30° and 0.1 M (NaClO_4) ionic strength have been investigated by Calvin-Bjerrum pH titration technique as modified by Irving and Rossotti. The effect of ionic strength on proton (pK) and metal ligand stability constant ($\log K$) is observed by examining the system at $\mu=0.029$ M, 0.049 M, 0.069 M, 0.089 M and 0.109 M. The influence of the solvent is studied by evaluating pK and $\log K$ values in 10%, 25%, 40%, 60% and 75% (v/v) dioxane-water mixtures.

All the reagents used were of AR quality. The method of purification of dioxane, the procedure employed and the methods used for the calculations of $\bar{n}_A$, $\bar{n}$, pK and $\log K$ are the same as given earlier⁷.

Results and Discussion

pK and $\log K_1$ values (Table 1) decrease with an increase of ionic strength. The data were analysed by the Bronsted equation

$$\log K = \log K^\circ + A\Delta Z^2 \sqrt{\mu}$$

The plots of pK and $\log K$ vs $\sqrt{\mu}$ were linear.

TABLE 1—ACID DISSOCIATION CONSTANTS OF SALICYLALDEHYDE AND STABILITY CONSTANTS OF URANYL CHELATES WITH SALICYLALDEHYDE

μ	pK	μ	$\log K_1$
0.029	12.69	0.031	12.01
0.049	12.54	0.071	11.71
0.069	12.46	0.110	11.43
0.089	12.37		
0.109	12.31		

Accuracy 0.02 to 0.05.

Knowing $A=6.78^8$ the magnitude of ΔZ^2 was calculated which is given below :

Reaction	ΔZ^2 values	
	obs.	calc.
$\text{HL} \rightleftharpoons \text{H}^+ + \text{L}^-$	-2.26	2
$\text{UO}_2^{2+} + \text{HL} \rightleftharpoons \text{UO}_2\text{L}^+ + \text{H}^+$	-2.07	2

By making use of modified Bronsted-Christian

equation⁹ $\log K = \log K^\circ + \frac{A\Delta Z^2 \sqrt{\mu}}{1 + Ba \sqrt{\mu}}$ in which size

of ions were obtained by trial method [$a=7\text{\AA}$ for salicylaldehyde, and $a=6\text{\AA}$ for $\text{UO}_2(\text{VI})$ salicylaldehyde], the observed linearity between pK

vs $\frac{\sqrt{\mu}}{5.39\sqrt{\mu}}$ and $\log K$, vs $\frac{\sqrt{\mu}}{1+4.62\sqrt{\mu}}$ for both

systems respectively was much better than given by earlier plots. The plots gave value of $A\Delta Z^2$ for salicylaldehyde and for $\text{UO}_2(\text{VI})$ -salicylaldehyde as 13.54 and 13.11 respectively which did not show any appreciable improvement over the previous values.

The values of thermodynamic constants obtained from the plots of $pK/\log K$ vs $\frac{\sqrt{\mu}}{1+Ba\sqrt{\mu}}$ are in agreement with the theoretical values. These values are as follows :

Salicylaldehyde	$pK^\circ = 13.90$
$\text{UO}_2(\text{VI})$ -Salicylaldehyde	$\log K_1^\circ = 13.25$

Effect of the dielectric constant of the medium :

For the purpose of investigating the effect of dielectric constant on the complexation reaction, the two systems were studied in 10%, 25%, 60% and 75% (v/v) dioxane-water mixtures. The values of pK , $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ increase with an increase in the percentage of dioxane (Table 2). The plots of

$pK/\log K_1$ vs $\frac{1}{D}$ and plots of pK and $\log K_1$ vs mole fraction are found to be linear.

TABLE 2—ACID DISSOCIATION CONSTANTS OF SALICYLALDEHYDE AND STABILITY CONSTANTS OF URANYL CHELATE WITH SALICYLALDEHYDE

% Dioxane	Temp. = 30°C		$\mu = 0.1M \text{ NaClO}_4$		Medium = 75% (v/v) dioxane-water			
	Mole fraction	pK		$\log K_1$		$\log K_2$		
		Practical	Thermodynamic	Practical	Thermodynamic	Practical	Thermodynamic	
10	0.0296	8.53	8.64	6.68	6.79	5.88	5.99	
25	0.0650	8.84	9.01	8.60	7.40	7.35	6.52	
40	0.1233	9.16	9.51	7.18	8.13	6.66	7.01	
60	0.2410	9.77	10.66	8.35	9.24	7.33	8.22	
75	0.3870	10.15	12.03	9.26	11.16	8.11	10.01	

Accuracy 0.02 to 0.05.

Calculation of the radius of the ion :

The effective ionic radius of the ligand anion was obtained by the Born equation¹⁰. The plot of $\Delta pK(pK_{\text{mix}} - pK_{\text{water}})$ against $\frac{1}{D}$ was found to be linear. The effective ionic radius obtained from the slope of the linear plot was 0.82 Å for salicylaldehyde. The value observed is of the same order in magnitude as that obtained by Ohtaki¹¹ for oxalate and ammonium ions. The very low magnitude of the ionic radius may be due to the fact that this value does not give the size of the whole organic molecule but that of charged site, i.e. hydroxyl oxygen in salicylaldehyde molecule.

References

1. E. PELIGOT, *J. Prac. Chem.*, 1945, **35**, 153.
2. I. FELDMAN and J. R. HAVILL, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, **76**, 2114.
3. I. FELDMAN, J. R. HAVILL and W. F. NEUMAN, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, **76**, 4726.
4. S. HAKAMORI, *Chem. Abs.*, 1932, **26**, 2366.
5. R. S. RAJAN and A. E. MARTELL, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1964, **26**, 789.
6. D. V. JAHAGIRDAR and D. D. KHANOLKAR, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1973, **35**, 921.
7. V. G. RATOLIKAR, D. V. JAHAGIRDAR and D. D. KHANOLKAR, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1978, **16A**, 510.
8. H. S. HARNED and B. B. OWEN, 'Physical Chemistry of Electrolytic Solutions, 2nd Edition, Reinhold Publications, Corp., New York, 1950, p. 547.
9. S. K. SINHA and S. S. KATTIYAR, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1970, **74**, 1382.
10. F. FRANKS and D. I. G. IVES, *Quart. Rev.*, 1966, **20**, 1.
11. H. OHTAKI, *Bull. Chem. Soc., Japan*, 1969, **42**, 1573.

Studies of Formation Constants of Lanthanoid Complexes with N-Benzoylphenyl Hydroxylamine

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THE determination of the formation constant values for the rare earth complexes with organic ligands containing active oxygen atom have aroused interest because of the flexibility of the coordination number of the rare earth ions. In contrast, the nature of the lanthanide-hydroxamate bond interaction remained unexplored. In this paper, the formation constant values of five lanthanide ions with N-benzoylphenylhydroxylamine (N-BPHA), determined in dioxane-water medium (3 : 1 v/v), are reported.

The chemicals used were of either E. Merck, G. R., B.D.H. or AR grade. Doubly distilled water (CO₂ free) and purified dioxane¹ were used. The perchlorates of lanthanides used were prepared by digesting the corresponding oxides (99.9% pure, Johnson Matthey) with perchloric acid and removing the excess acid by repeated evaporation under an electrical heater. Finally the perchlorates were dissolved in water and made up to a definite volume. Lanthanide ions were determined by oxalate precipitation and their subsequent ignition to their respective oxides². Free perchloric acid present in the metal perchlorate solutions were determined by running a known volume of the solution through a column of Amberlite IR-120 (H⁺-form) and titrating the liberated acid with a standard sodium hydroxide solution.

N-Benzoylphenylhydroxylamine (N-BPHA) : The reagent was prepared by the method as described earlier³. Before use, the reagent was repeatedly